

VALUE RELEVANCE OF SOCIAL COST CONTRIBUTION ON HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT: A FOCAL POINT OF SUB-SAHARAN AFRICAN COUNTRIES

Ude, Alexander Onyebuchi Ph.D., FCEnt, CNA

Department of Accounting, Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria

Ugwu, James Ike Ph.D., CNA*

Department of Accounting, Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria

*Corresponding author

Adebayo, Gbenga Ayodele, Ph.D.

Department of Accounting, Confluence University of Science and Technology, Osara, Kogi State Nigeria

Ogidiolu Arinomo Rita

Department of Business Education, College of Education, Ankpa, Kogi State, Nigeria

Idih, Ogwu Emmanuel, Ph.D.

Department of Banking and Finance, Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria.

Edoka, Reuben Ogbaje, Ph.D.

Department of Banking and Finance, Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria.

Abstract

The pursuit of economic growth and societal progress in Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries hinges upon robust investments in human capital development. This paper delves into the value relevance of social cost contributions in shaping education and healthcare outcomes within SSA. Education is unveiled as a transformative force, fostering innovation, gender empowerment, and economic mobility. Yet, challenges in education provision persist, necessitating targeted interventions. Social cost contributions emerge as catalysts for change, invigorating educational infrastructure, teacher training, and curricular enhancements. Similarly, healthcare's pivotal role in economic productivity and societal well-being is illuminated. While SSA faces healthcare challenges, data-driven analyses reveal the correlation between healthcare investments and economic growth. Social cost contributions drive innovative healthcare solutions, from telemedicine to community health worker programs. The empirical exploration of healthcare and education data underscores governments' commitment to nurturing healthier, more educated populations. Amidst challenges, this study highlights the transformative power of social cost contributions in propelling SSA countries toward inclusive growth, empowerment, and sustainable progress. The study recommends that SSA nations should sustain and possibly improve on their social expenditure on education and the current strategy in education management for continuous improvement on school enrolment and literacy level while efforts on providing health care services like mobile health care and immunization should be sustained and improved by various government in SSA hence the need for increased health care funding.

Keywords: Social cost contributions, human capital development, Sub-Saharan Africa, education, healthcare, economic growth, societal progress

Introduction

Human capital is the foundational element to progress — both inherently in terms of human dignity and livelihood, as well practically speaking with collapse-proof building blocks. It comprises the common capability, knowledge and health of individuals as a source for all forms creative practices (Danquah & Amankwah-Amoah, 2017). Human capital comes into sharper focus -- especially among Sub Saharan African countries which face unique challenges on their developmental journey. It is undeniable, the potential for growth and progression in Sub Saharan African countries. The halfway to support human capital is really a long challenging change. Notable examples include weaknesses in availability of good quality education, inadequate healthcare infrastructure and wide spread socio-economic disparities (Ogundari & Awokuse 2018). These manifest in low employability opportunities, muted innovational potential and stunted economic output for which a targeted response is imperative with regard to human capital development.

The research, therefore, is guided by the question of the dynamic relationship between social cost contributions and augmentation to human capital development in Sub-Saharan African countries. Decoding the relative importance of these contributions and their mitigating power is of interest. This effort is therefore aligned with a growing body of research demonstrating the transformative power of well-targeted social investments. This paper is coherently structured, dealing with the conceptual underpinning of social cost contributions and the manner in which they are directly related to human capital development at the very outset. Further sections are dedicated to the unique fields of education and healthcare, detailing the effects of investment in both. We will also take a closer look at the intricate relationship between economic productivity and human capital, based on empirical data dating from 2000 onwards. We also illustrate the potential to mobilize social cost contributions for the development of sustainable human capital and discuss the implications. The paper is well concluded by synthesizing key insights and emphasizing transformative potentials of strategic investments.

Research methodology

This research approach combines qualitative case studies and literature evaluation with quantitative macro-level data analysis using hybrid techniques. The World Bank's World Development Indicators (WDI) database offers worldwide comparable education and health statistics, hence sourcing the quantitative data from there (World Bank, 2021). The choice of this database was determined by its dependability, broad coverage of nations under the SSA, and use of consistent data collecting methods throughout several nations and historical eras. The research selected elements related to the development of human capital in the domains of healthcare and education as well as to the contributions to society expenses. The study examined government expenditure on education as a proportion of the GDP, school enrolment rates, literacy rates, healthcare spending, and newborn mortality rates. These indicators were chosen depending on their applicability to our study subjects and their general frequency in the body of development economics literature (Ogundari & Awokuse, 2018; Atun et al., 2017). The study spanning 2000 to 2020 exposes long-standing patterns and the effects of actions over a long span. It was chosen to

represent the results of important worldwide projects like early Sustainable Development Goals and the Millennium Development Goals.

Social Cost Contributions and Human Capital Development

The contributions to social cost and human capital development are intertwined, revealing a strategic approach toward solving some of the pressing problems in Sub-Saharan African countries. Social cost contributions refer to the financial investments made by governments, organizations, or stakeholders toward the betterment of social issues such as education, healthcare, and poverty. It is in such investments that the real development of human capital lies, because they enable human beings with education, access to healthcare, and a platform from which to rise economically. That basically means the cost of not addressing social issues overshadows many times the expenditure required to alleviate them. It is in this direction—poverty alleviation, health, and education—that the social cost contributions attempt to break out of the intergenerational poverty cycle by promoting sustainable human development.

In the broader sense, social cost contributions illustrate the intersection of public and private sector initiatives for positive social change. It is led by governments with an investment of public funds to drive social change, while at the same time, private entities do so through embracing corporate social responsibility means, philanthropic, and collaborative ways of enhancing their business beyond profit making through social impact.

The importance of social cost contributions extends beyond the money involved; it holds within itself an implied acknowledgment of the interrelationship among societal welfare, economic growth, and democracy. The holistic view acknowledges that a society that is healthy and educated will translate into an effective workforce with reduced healthcare costs and more optimal conditions for business. Therefore, social cost contributions go beyond the conventional understanding of charity or aid by exhibiting strategic investment in people's and nations' long-term prosperity.

In a nutshell, social cost contributions are societies moving investments towards new strategies that envision both economic growth and social advancement as inseparable goals. This new approach defines more than philanthropy and aid in speaking to intentional, structured investment for raising human capital, reducing societal challenges, and setting the way forward clearly into the future. In particular, in Sub-Saharan African countries, social cost contributions can help subdue serious challenges that many such countries face within their education and health sectors. As a matter of fact, a view of the empirical evidence obtained from such studies points out the reasons as to why there is a dire need for large investments in their educational infrastructure and healthcare services. The social cost contributions reflect an important solution towards covering such lapses in having quality education and access to basic healthcare, with a large part of the population lacking these services (Gershman, 2016).

Education as a Social cost

Education is the backbone in the development of human capital and serves to act as a promoter for economic growth and social progress, as well as human empowerment. These educational gaps, when seen in the context of Sub-Saharan African nations alone, underscore education's role as a driver of transformation. The following section elaborates on how education can produce multidimensional benefits, the problems the region is facing, and the critical turnaround contribution that social cost makes in the improvement of education outcomes.

The Multifaceted Benefits of Education

Sub-Saharan African countries face a myriad of problems that impede the provision of quality education to all sections of their people (Bvumbwe & Mtshali, 2018). Poor infrastructure, with old school buildings and lack of technology access, greatly affect the quality of learning spaces (Mtebe, 2015). Teacher shortages which are global problems particularly so in Sub-Saharan Africa has remained a strong impediment to the efficient transmission of knowledge and skills (Aborode et al., 2020). For example, in Nigeria, the number of qualified teachers is diminishing leading to large class sizes and limited individualized attention (Asamoah & Mackin, 2015) while the lack of professional opportunities for teachers inhibits their capacity for innovation in teaching and learning (Lauwerier & Akkari, 2015). Economic disparities in Sub-Saharan African countries also compound the problem of equity in education (Basak & Govender, 2015). Poor communities do not have access to quality education due to a lack of financial resources thus causing the majority of the population to be deprived of an education. Furthermore, cultural norms and gender discrimination affects education negatively, particularly that of females (Basak & Govender, 2015). Socio-cultural factors may lead to a perception that girls should not have equal access as boys and this would hinder their growth both personally and professionally.

Challenges in Providing Quality Education

Sub-Saharan African countries face a myriad of problems that impede the provision of quality education to all sections of their people (Bvumbwe & Mtshali, 2018). Poor infrastructure, with old school buildings and lack of technology access, greatly affect the quality of learning spaces (Mtebe, 2015). Additionally, absence of teaching and learning resources such as textbooks and interactive learning materials further perpetuate difficulties for both teachers and learners. According to Ndlovu-Gatsheni (2017), colonialism still greatly affects the educational institutions of Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), which results in the creation of curriculum that fail to sufficiently represent the local needs and culture. asongu and Odhiambo (2019) also discovered that education in several SSA countries suffer from poor funding. In remote locations, insufficient finance results in poor facilities, limited instructional tools, and challenges attracting and keeping instructors. Economic differences cause children from low-income homes in Sub-Saharan African (SSA) nations more difficulty obtaining enough schooling (Bashir et al., 2018). Bashir et al., (2018) further highlighted the fact that Social attitudes and behaviours might hinder universal education especially with regard to underprivileged areas. These linked issues need for thorough solutions combining the sociopolitical setting of SSA's educational institutions with political aspects.

Economic disparities in Sub-Saharan African countries compound the problem of equity in education (Basak & Govender, 2015). Poor communities do not have access to quality education due to a lack of financial resources thus causing the majority of the population to be deprived of an education. Furthermore, cultural norms and gender discrimination affects education negatively, particularly that of females (Basak & Govender, 2015). Socio-cultural factors may lead to a perception that girls should not have equal access as boys and this would hinder their growth both personally and professionally.

Empirical analysis of social cost contributions in enhancing education

The potential of social cost contributions in enhancing education within the countries of Sub-Saharan Africa has to be assessed considering the multi-faceted challenges that would have wrecked the educational systems. World Bank data reveal a dynamic relationship between government expenditure on education, school enrolment growth rate, and literacy rates for the

youth of 2021. All these indicators give a glimpse into the effectiveness of social cost contributions in enhancing educational development.

Figure 1: Social cost contribution to Education

A closer look at the data from 2001 to 2020 shows fluctuations in government expenditure on education in SSA. Growth rates in 2002-2003 and 2006-2011, in particular, suggest surges that can be related to heightened investment in education, most likely due to increased social cost contributions. These positive trends are accordingly in line with related initiatives focused on improving educational outcomes by using targeted funding. Analysis of the data indicates that generally, the negative rates in growth in school enrollment match up against economic challenges or uprisings in society. This reveals that an education system can easily be affected by external factors. Contrary to this, with respect to the positive growth rates in enrollment, it is suggested that improvements made in access to education, more specifically in the 2000s and 2014 onwards, may have been driven by social cost contributions addressing enrollment barriers. On literacy outcome, data reveals fluctuations of the youth literacy rate over the years. Positive growth rates, mainly during the early 2000s and from 2014 to 2016, match periods of positive educational investment and probable additions of social cost that might have targeted literacy programs. In summary, data from the SSA region reaffirms the complex interplay between government expenditure on education, school enrollment growth rates, and youth literacy rates. Trends of the indicators point out that social cost contributions could have positive effects on education: breaking barriers to enrollment, creating an enabling learning environment, and increasing literacy rates. The data also underlines those educational systems are susceptible to external factors; therefore, there is a need for sustained strategic social cost contributions in order to propel educational development in SSA.

Case study successful educational intervention

One excellent example of a worthy social cost contribution in the sphere of education is Northern Ghana's School for Life (SfL) initiative. This 1995 experiment shows how focused interventions might assist to solve educational problems in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). The programming's cultural sensitivity and community-based approach help to explain its success. Conducted in indigenous languages, sessions for the Sustainable Farming and Livelihood (SfL) program provide flexible plans fit for agricultural cycles and community requirements. In underprivileged communities, this strategy has greatly improved schooling. Akyeampong et al. (2012) claim that since the initiative began, 65% of more than 120,000 students have effectively moved to traditional primary schools and finished their education.

SfL influences more than merely numeracy and reading. Hartwell (2012) performed a longitudinal research showing that participants in SfL (Skills for Life) programs had greater engagement in community events and better cognitive skills than those who did not finish the courses. The project improved female educational parity as well. Casely-Hayford and Ghartey (2007) found that the SfL program accounted for one-third of Ghanaian primary education costs per kid. The effectiveness of resource use shows how effectively organised social cost contributions could improve the educational return on investment. One may admit that the SfL program is successful. It has been replicated elsewhere in Ghana and shaped teaching strategies in other West African nations (Mfum-Mensah, 2011). Customised social cost contributions, considering particular local situations and needs, might assist to remove educational obstacles in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) and have wider effects outside of immediate learning results.

Healthcare: Investments and Impact

It means that human capital development in health echoes on several dimensions where only a healthy population is capable of forming the basis of attaining economic productivity, creating innovation, and fostering the welfare of a society as a whole. Apart from ensuring the health of individuals, access to quality healthcare directly contributes to national economic prosperity and progress (Deaton & Tortora, 2015). It is seen that if people are provided with health care services that prevent, treat and manage sickness, they are able to contribute better to the economy, claim Deaton & Tortora, 2015. Less absenteeism levels in work due to sickness, lesser health-related costs borne by the employers and improved overall work performance all add up and result in high productivity for the economy. Studies have proved that healthier nations have higher growth and stability in their economies as healthy people are likely to actively participate in the workforce and increase the level of output.

It is also a means of developing innovation and knowledge-based economies. Healthy people have better opportunities for education, research, and entrepreneurship. A good healthcare system provides security to encourage people to be innovative and take risks, knowing that they can follow up new ideas without constantly worrying about health-related setbacks. It is seen that if the access to preventive care and timely medical interventions is made available, not only will well-being be fostered, but also an environment will be created that will aid creativity, discovery, and technological advancement.

Further, the intrinsic relationship between healthcare access and economic growth becomes the key building block of a prosperous nation. People benefit from quality healthcare that prevents, manages, and treats illnesses and their productivity towards contributing to their country's economy is enhanced. The relation which makes health improve one's productivity is not some hypothetical supposition but an empirically posited assertion which is heavily entrenched in diverse studies and anecdotal experiences. Many studies have pointed out the direct relationship that exists between accessible healthcare and robust economic growth. Take, for example, a study by Aboderin and Beard in which they surveyed the impact of an investment in healthcare on economic indicators in many developing countries. There was found to be a persuasive association between increased expenditure on health and higher GDP growth rates. This relationship is not based only on the decrease of absenteeism related to healthcare issues, but it also leads to an improved work performance because of better health outcomes (Atun et al., 2017).

This, in turn, has ripple effects across all sectors of the economy. Healthier people are more likely to be actively involved in the labor market and workplace. As the cases of illness-based absenteeism greatly reduce, efficiency at work soars, hence directly affecting the base levels of output in economies¹. Furthermore, it is observed that in situations of economic crises, healthier nations are more resilient, as healthy individuals are better equipped to withstand adversity and help the economy recover from a slump (Makuta & O'Hare, 2015). A clear example can be taken from the case of South Africa, where continuous health investing resulted in massive reductions in absenteeism related to bad health (Tzenios, 2019). This decline translated into increased labor force participation and upsurged economic productivity. The case of South Africa epitomizes how strategic investments in health can pay off tangibly in the economy.

Innovative research also brings out the deep relationship that exists between accessible healthcare and innovation-driven economies. In a study by Kyei-Nimakoh et al., it was reviewed that the complex nexus of health and innovation showed that healthier populations have a greater propensity to engage in educational pursuits, research activities, and even entrepreneurship. This synergy between health and innovation is not coincidental; a strong health system becomes a safety net that induces most people to pursue innovative ideas without the fear of setbacks in health status. Having timely medical interventions and preventive care builds people's confidence to pursue innovation, which in the end, contributes to technological advancement and economic growth.

Data from 2000 to 2020 also provides insights into the critical role of social cost contributions in shaping healthcare outcomes and their subsequent impact on human capital (Worldbank, 2021).

It simply reflects that, despite differences in the magnitude of expenditure on health as a share of GDP, there is a common commitment to healthcare across the region. That affects healthcare investment only if the allocation is efficient and interventions are targeted. In that sense, the commitment may be regarded as a recognition by governments of the central role that health plays in the development of human capital, economic growth, and societal progress. Regionally, spending on healthcare has risen linearly from lows in the early 2000s when it accounted for around 5% of GDP. There is an occasional jig on the later years—including its peak in 2003 and then its modest troughs and recoveries—the overall trend is one of sustained recognition for investment in this key area of healthcare (Kyei-Nimakoh et al., 2017). Notably, this streak of consistent funding is evidence of the dedication by the SSA countries in transforming the quality of healthcare and realizing the transformational benefits of a healthy population.

Among other big problems in the provision of quality healthcare within SSA, there have been resource constraints and a high burden of infectious diseases (Makuta & O'Hare, 2015). This is a major problem facing many SSA nations; many medical resources, including trained medical personnel, are readily unavailable. The worst hit are rural and disadvantaged areas where healthcare facilities and trained medical professionals do not exist. For instance, in Nigeria, a rural community in a far-flung region of the country means that residents of this village have to travel far before getting to a hospital. This not only creates logistical problems due to a lack of proximity to medical facilities but has, many times, exacerbated health conditions and delayed medical interventions, resulting in less effective treatment options.

As a result of this bottleneck, healthcare outcomes turn negative. Poor prenatal care and high maternal mortality rates are attributed to pregnant women who have no access to centres for maternal healthcare, hence making maternal and child health vulnerable to the threat as well. In a similar manner, children in the rural areas find it harder to be immunized, which can later lead to higher cases of disease.

Through advances in technology and community engagement, governments and organisations within SSA have implemented innovative solutions that combat such issues. Mobile health clinics, for example, integrate the power of telemedicine to increase access to healthcare in places like Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania. According to Meyer-Weitz et al. in 2018, this means

that such programs, linking people in remote areas with specialists, enhance access to timely care.

Moreover, community health workers play a very vital role in extending primary healthcare to underserved communities in society. With some amount of training and basic medical equipment, these community health workers can bring remote communities into contact with mainstream medical services. They can ensure basic healthcare reaches those who need it most and reduce most of the bad impacts of poor accessibility.

On their part, governments are showing commitment to investing in health infrastructure to enhance accessibility. For example, Ethiopia has started a wholesale program in establishing and upgrading health facilities in the rural setting to ensure easy access to quality healthcare services. Aggressiveness in this way not only solves the challenge of inaccessibility but also sets a base for health development that can be sustained. It also shows undulations in the current health expenditure as a percentage of GDP. This definitely further illustrates the dynamics involved in healthcare financing and the difficulty of ensuring constant investment. This volatility in healthcare expenditure can have direct effects on access to healthcare services and their quality, consequently affecting the health of individuals and, as such, the human capital pool.

Impression

From the analysis of the data, as could be seen from the graphs, these impressions were made:

1. There has been undulating movement on the social contribution to education and its influence on the literacy rate and school enrolment in SSA; there is, however, a continuous improvement in government expenditure on education with an associated positive change in school enrolment and literacy rate since 2018.
2. There has been some progress toward reduction in infant mortality rates in SSA. This is evidenced from the slope of the graph, which shows a downward trend in mortality since 2000.

Conclusion

The intricate interplay between social cost contributions and human capital development is the mainstay or cornerstone of sustainable progress for the Sub-Saharan African countries. In SSA, education stands a chance to occupy the podium of hope, sparking flames in innovation, productivity, and social mobility. It is multifaceted benefits accruing from education, equipping people with skills, inculcating critical thinking, and gender empowerment that underpin its potential to act as a driver for economic development. On the other side, however, a myriad of problems beset the education landscape in this region, not to mention inadequate infrastructure and shortages of teachers. The impact of social cost contributions has manifested itself through changed educative infrastructures and human resource capabilities. Health, on the other hand, is an inherent factor during the creation of human capital. It is considered the base of economic production and the vehicle for social advancement. A healthy population nourishes innovation, propels economic growth, and significantly improves well-being. There is a rising trend in telemedicine programs, community health worker initiatives, and spending on infrastructure for better health access and outcomes.

The empirical analysis of the data on health and education observed between 2000 and 2020 further elucidates the complicated interaction of social cost contributions with the development of human capital. In such a way, the trends in expenditure on health and in educational investments incorporate the commitments of governments to the nourishment of healthier and

more educated populations. Nonetheless, it is not without challenges, which again underscores the major role of consistent effort and optimal resource allocation for any real change to be realized. The relevance of social cost contributions towards human capital development in SSA is not trivial. As pivotal pillars, education and health are intertwined; together they form the backbone of a prosperous future. From analysis of the data presented in this paper, insights emerge on the transforming power of directed investments and strategic interventions. While challenges remain, the case studies and empirical analyses show that social cost contributions can potentially bridge gaps, empower individuals, and propel nations toward inclusive growth. Considering the growth trajectory of the SSA countries and the high rate of development accompanying it, an emphasis on education and health by making social cost contributions becomes very important.

Recommendations

It is on this basis that the study recommends as follows:

1. The SSA nations should maintain and probably improve the current level of social expenditure on education, and the strategy in managing school enrolment for continuous improvement in school enrolment and literacy level.
2. The current expenditure on health should be increased to maintain and improve the trend. This is because there is population growth, which should be matched with corresponding health services. Efforts to reach rural areas, like mobile health clinics and immunization usually by community health extension workers, should be sustained. These will keep the infant mortality rate on a downward trend.

Limitation

This study clarifies the relevance of social cost contributions for the growth of human capital in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). The results' generalisability and interpretation might be hampered, nonetheless, by various constraints. Though the WDI database of the World Bank offers a whole picture, it could hide important national variations across nations. Jerven (2013) pointed out that restrictions in the capacity of national statistics agencies might compromise the reliability and quality of economic data from underdeveloped nations. This restriction could skew our study and lead to measurement errors. Moreover, it is essential to prove a causal link between the results of human capital and the expenses to society. Although trends and connections abound, it is crucial to keep in mind that human capital development is a complicated process affected by various confusing elements. Deaton (2010) contends that it is difficult to ascertain the effect of policy initiatives without national randomised controlled trials.

The possible bias the choice of case studies and novels brings might potentially affect our results. Although we tried to pick wisely, intervention studies with favourable results might be disproportionately shown. The ultimate differences in political systems, economic growth, and social structures across SSA nations limit the relevance of our results. Developing broad policy suggestions has inherent hazards because the success of a certain strategy in one nation or area may not necessarily be translocated to another (Rodrik, 2008).

Implication For Future Direction

The results of our research have major effects on Sub-Saharan African policy and development. Especially in the spheres of education and healthcare, they underline the importance of ongoing, concentrated financial contributions towards the development of human capital. Using these

results calls for careful local study of the particular situation and difficulties. Implementing thorough plans for the development of human capital depends on this. Our studies show that spending on healthcare and education have a favourable correlation. Policymakers should therefore consider the interconnection of these two sectors and create thorough plans covering both. Drake et al. (2017) claim that health check-ups and school nutrition programs—two cross-sectoral initiatives—have been effectively adopted by Ghana and Kenya.

Using creative financial strategies might help to improve contributions towards society expenses. Many of the governments in Sub-Saharan Africa have limited budgets. As such, impact bonds, public-private alliances, and diaspora bonds might provide more money for the growth of human capital (Ketkar & Ratha, 2010). Our case studies show that focused interventions are successful, suggesting that in Sub-Saharan Africa decentralised education and healthcare delivery can be more successful. This implies that rather than depending on national plans, it is more advantageous to provide local communities the power to satisfy the particular needs of every location (Westhorp et al., 2014). The investigation of additional categories should take front stage in future studies. First of all, longitudinal research is crucial to have a more complete knowledge of how social cost contributions affect human capital results over time. These results might help to clarify the long-term effectiveness and persistent effects of treatments. Moreover, it is advised that future studies should examine national-level data in a method that divides it into smaller parts to evaluate the contribution of every area to the societal cost. Additional thorough studies conducted at the regional or community level might reveal some excellent strategies that could be enlarged on a more general basis.

REFERENCES

- Aboderin, I. A., & Beard, J. R. (2015). Older people's health in sub-Saharan Africa. *The Lancet*, 385(9968), e9-e11.
- Aborode, A., Anifowoshe, O., Ayodele, T. I., Ireiyayo, A. R., & David, O. O. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 on education in sub-Saharan Africa.
- Acemoglu, D., & Robinson, J. A. (2012). *Why nations fail: The origins of power, prosperity, and poverty*. Crown Business.
- Akyeampong, K., Djangmah, J., Oduro, A., Seidu, A., & Hunt, F. (2007). Access to basic education in Ghana: The evidence and the issues. CREATE Country Analytic Review. University of Sussex.
- Arndt, C., McKay, A., & Tarp, F. (2016). *Growth and poverty in sub-Saharan Africa* (p. 528). Oxford University Press.
- Asamoah, M. K., & Mackin, E. E. (2015). Breaking the fetters of higher education in Sub-Saharan Africa. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 7(1), 6-16.
- Asongu, S. A., & Nwachukwu, J. C. (2018). Educational quality thresholds in the diffusion of knowledge with mobile phones for inclusive human development in sub-Saharan Africa. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 129, 164-172.
- Asongu, S. A., & Odhiambo, N. M. (2019). Basic formal education quality, information technology, and inclusive human development in sub-Saharan Africa. *Sustainable Development*, 27(3), 419-428.
- Asongu, S. A., & Odhiambo, N. M. (2020). The role of governance in quality education in sub-Saharan Africa. *International Social Science Journal*, 70(237-238), 221-238.

- Atun, R., Davies, J. I., Gale, E. A., Bärnighausen, T., Beran, D., Kengne, A. P., ... & Werfalli, M. (2017). Diabetes in sub-Saharan Africa: from clinical care to health policy. *The lancet Diabetes & endocrinology*, 5(8), 622-667.
- Atun, R., Davies, J. I., Gale, E. A., Bärnighausen, T., Beran, D., Kengne, A. P., ... & Werfalli, M. (2017). Diabetes in sub-Saharan Africa: from clinical care to health policy. *The Lancet Diabetes & Endocrinology*, 5(8), 622-667.
- Ayega, D. (2020). Pandemics and education in Sub-Saharan Africa: Invest in education technology. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 8(8), 581-586.
- Bailey, C., Blake, C., Schriver, M., Cubaka, V. K., Thomas, T., & Martin Hilber, A. (2016). A systematic review of supportive supervision as a strategy to improve primary healthcare services in Sub-Saharan Africa. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics*, 132(1), 117-125.
- Basak, S. K., & Govender, D. W. (2015). Development of a conceptual framework regarding the factors inhibiting teachers successful adoption and implementation of ICT in teaching and learning. *International Business & Economics Research Journal (IBER)*, 14(3), 431-438.
- Bashir, S., Lockheed, M., Ninan, E., & Tan, J. P. (2018). Facing forward: Schooling for learning in Africa. The World Bank.
- Bvumbwe, T., & Mtshali, N. (2018). Nursing education challenges and solutions in Sub Saharan Africa: an integrative review. *BMC nursing*, 17(1), 1-11.
- Casely-Hayford, L., & Ghartey, A. B. (2007). The leap to literacy and life change in Northern Ghana: An impact assessment of School for Life (SfL). Accra: School for Life.
- Casely-Hayford, L., & Hartwell, A. (2010). Reaching the underserved with complementary education: lessons from Ghana's state and non-state sectors. *Development in Practice*, 20(4-5), 527-539.
- Danquah, M., & Amankwah-Amoah, J. (2017). Assessing the relationships between human capital, innovation and technology adoption: Evidence from sub-Saharan Africa. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 122, 24-33.
- Deaton, A. (2010). Instruments, randomization, and learning about development. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 48(2), 424-455.
- Deaton, A. S., & Tortora, R. (2015). People in sub-Saharan Africa rate their health and health care among the lowest in the world. *Health Affairs*, 34(3), 519-527.
- Delery, J. E., & Roumpi, D. (2017). Strategic human resource management, human capital and competitive advantage: is the field going in circles?. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 27(1), 1-21.
- DeStefano, J., Moore, A. S., Balwanz, D., & Hartwell, A. (2007). Reaching the underserved: Complementary models of effective schooling. Academy for Educational Development.
- Donou-Adonsou, F. (2019). Technology, education, and economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Telecommunications policy*, 43(4), 353-360.
- Drake, L., Fernandes, M., Aurino, E., Kiamba, J., Giyose, B., Burbano, C., ... & Gelli, A. (2017). School feeding programs in middle childhood and adolescence. In *Disease Control Priorities, (Volume 8): Child and Adolescent Health and Development*. The World Bank.
- Esfijani, A., & Zamani, B. E. (2020). Factors influencing teachers' utilisation of ICT: The role of in-service training courses and access. *Research in Learning Technology*, 28.
- Gershman, B. (2016). Witchcraft beliefs and the erosion of social capital: Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa and beyond. *Journal of Development Economics*, 120, 182-208.

- Hanushek, E. A., & Woessmann, L. (2012). Do better schools lead to more growth? Cognitive skills, economic outcomes, and causation. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 17(4), 267-321.
- Hartwell, A. (2012). Learning for all: Alternative models and policy options. In A. Verger, M. Novelli, & H. K. Altinyelken (Eds.), *Global Education Policy and International Development: New Agendas, Issues and Policies* (pp. 141-164). Bloomsbury Academic.
- Harvie, D., Lightfoot, G., Lilley, S., & Weir, K. (2021). Social investment innovation and the 'social turn' of neoliberal finance. *Critical Perspectives on Accounting*, 79, 102248.
- Ilie, S., & Rose, P. (2016). Is equal access to higher education in South Asia and sub-Saharan Africa achievable by 2030?. *Higher Education*, 72, 435-455.
- Ingutia, R., Reztis, A. N., & Sumelius, J. (2020). Child poverty, status of rural women and education in sub Saharan Africa. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 111, 104869.
- Jerven, M. (2013). *Poor numbers: How we are misled by African development statistics and what to do about it*. Cornell University Press.
- Ketkar, S. L., & Ratha, D. (2010). Diaspora bonds: Tapping the diaspora during difficult times. *Journal of International Commerce, Economics and Policy*, 1(02), 251-263.
- Kyei-Nimakoh, M., Carolan-Olah, M., & McCann, T. V. (2017). Access barriers to obstetric care at health facilities in sub-Saharan Africa—a systematic review. *Systematic reviews*, 6, 1-16.
- Lauwerier, T., & Akkari, A. (2015). Teachers and the quality of basic education in sub-Saharan Africa. *Education Research and Foresight: Working Papers Series*, 11, 1-11.
- Makuta, I., & O'Hare, B. (2015). Quality of governance, public spending on health and health status in Sub Saharan Africa: a panel data regression analysis. *BMC public health*, 15(1), 1-11.
- Meyer-Weitz, A., Oppong Asante, K., & Lukobeka, B. J. (2018). Healthcare service delivery to refugee children from the Democratic Republic of Congo living in Durban, South Africa: a caregivers' perspective. *BMC medicine*, 16, 1-12.
- Mfum-Mensah, O. (2011). Education collaboration to promote school participation in northern Ghana: A case study of a complementary education program. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 31(5), 465-471.
- Mtebe, J. (2015). Learning management system success: Increasing learning management system usage in higher education in sub-Saharan Africa. *International Journal of Education and Development using ICT*, 11(2).
- Ndlovu-Gatsheni, S. J. (2017). Decolonising research methodology must include undoing its dirty history. *Journal of Public Administration*, 52(1), 186-188.
- Ogundari, K., & Awokuse, T. (2018). Human capital contribution to economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa: does health status matter more than education?. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 58, 131-140.
- Ogundari, K., & Awokuse, T. (2018). Human capital contribution to economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa: Does health status matter more than education? *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 58, 131-140.
- Oketch, M. (2016). Financing higher education in sub-Saharan Africa: some reflections and implications for sustainable development. *Higher Education*, 72, 525-539.
- Ouane, A., & Glanz, C. (2010). *Why and how Africa should invest in African languages and multilingual education*. UNESCO Institute for Lifelong Learning.

- Psaki, S. R., McCarthy, K. J., & Mensch, B. S. (2018). Measuring gender equality in education: Lessons from trends in 43 countries. *Population and Development Review*, 44(1), 117-142.
- Raikes, A., Koziol, N., Davis, D., & Burton, A. (2020). Measuring quality of preprimary education in sub-Saharan Africa: Evaluation of the Measuring Early Learning Environments scale. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 53, 571-585.
- Rodrik, D. (2008). The new development economics: We shall experiment, but how shall we learn? HKS Working Paper No. RWP08-055.
- Schmidt-Traub, G., & Sachs, J. D. (2015). Financing sustainable development: implementing the SDGs through effective investment. *Sustainable Development Solution Network*. Retrieved from: <https://irp-cdn.multiscreensite.com/be6d1d56/files/uploaded/150619-SDSN-Financing-Sustainable-Development-Paper-FINAL-02.pdf>.
- Semo, B. W., & Frissa, S. M. (2020). The mental health impact of the COVID-19 pandemic: implications for sub-Saharan Africa. *Psychology research and behavior management*, 713-720.
- Sima, V., Gheorghe, I. G., Subić, J., & Nancu, D. (2020). Influences of the industry 4.0 revolution on the human capital development and consumer behavior: A systematic review. *Sustainability*, 12(10), 4035.
- Swanson, R. A. (2022). *Foundations of human resource development*. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- Tzenios, N. (2019). The Impact of Health Literacy on Employee Productivity: An Empirical Investigation. *Empirical Quests for Management Essences*, 3(1), 21-33.
- Westhorp, G., Walker, B., Rogers, P., Overbeeke, N., Ball, D., & Brice, G. (2014). Enhancing community accountability, empowerment and education outcomes in low and middle-income countries: A realist review. EPPI-Centre, Social Science Research Unit, Institute of Education, University of London.
- Willcox, M. L., Peersman, W., Daou, P., Diakit, C., Bajunirwe, F., Mubangizi, V., ... & Mant, D. (2015). Human resources for primary health care in sub-Saharan Africa: progress or stagnation?. *Human resources for health*, 13, 1-11.
- World Bank. (2021). World Development Indicators 2021. Retrieved from <https://databank.worldbank.org/reports.aspx?source=world-development-indicators>
- World Bank. (2021). World Development Indicators. Retrieved from <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators>
- Yeboah, I. E. (2018). Capitalism and sub-Saharan African human capital. *African Identities*, 16(1), 67-86.
- Zelasky, S. E., & Buonocore, J. J. (2021). The social costs of health-and climate-related on-road vehicle emissions in the continental United States from 2008 to 2017. *Environmental Research Letters*, 16(6), 065009.